

Precisely Patterned Nanofibers for
High Performance Bioseparations

DELIVERABLE 2.5: SPIDROIN MODELS

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SPIDROIN MODELS

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1. Introduction

Deliverable 2.5 regards the assessment of spidroin structures using molecular modeling techniques.

As an intrinsically disordered protein (IDP), spidroin model building was approached using AI (AlphaFold2) and *de novo* folding methods. Models of monomeric and tetrameric spidroins were assembled and studied with molecular dynamics simulations (MD) at an atomistic and coarse-grained level.

2. Spidroin modeling

Spidroin sequences were submitted to AlphaFold2 [1]. The obtained models presented a very low residue average pLDDT, and this approach was discarded.

A *de novo* approach was implemented by building the complete proteins in a linear structure, and then submitted to an MD run for a theoretical folding simulation of the three monomeric variants. This method originated “fibre-like” structures of spidroin monomers (Table 1).

Table 1 - Spidroin monomeric atomistic models after MD.

Spidroin monomers after MD	
Spidroin variants	Structure after MD
Spidroin 1	
Spidroin 2	
Spidroin 3	

To better understand the interactions between several monomers, a tetrameric version of each spidroin was assembled and submitted to an MD run. The final structures demonstrate that the tetrameric assemblies are stable throughout the MD simulation, Table 2. Furthermore, the tetrameric assemblies demonstrate some beta-sheet secondary structure (Figure 1). MD simulations were performed with Gromacs [2] and Amber99 [3] force field.

Table 2 - Spidroin tetrameric atomistic models after MD.

Spidroin tetramers after MD	
Spidroin variant	Structure after MD
Spidroin 1	
Spidroin 2	
Spidroin 3	

Figure 1 – Detail of beta-sheet secondary structure of spidroin 1 after 1ns MD.

3. Coarse-Grained models of Spidroins

To study the behaviour of Spidroin 1-3 at a coarse-grained level, the atomistic structures were translated to coarse-grained using the Martini v2.2 force field [4]. The bead models were submitted to a coarse-grained MD and revealed a different behaviour when comparing to the atomistic MDs. As observed in Table 3, the monomeric structures tend to stabilize in a globular shape, with the only exception being Spidroin 2.

Table 3 - Spidroin monomeric coarse-grained models after MD.

Spidroin monomers after Coarse-Grained MD	
Spidroin variant	Structure after MD
Spidroin 1	
Spidroin 2	
Spidroin 3	

These results suggest that a solvent with properties closer to the ones in spidroin solutions could prevent the monomer globularization at coarse-grained level.

The final studied model was a 100x100x100nm box with 500 spidroin 1 proteins. As observed in Figure 2, after 1µs of simulation the system creates a network/mesh of protein nanofibers. These nanofibers are stable and do not tend to form a fibre with a larger diameter.

Figure 1 – Spidroin multimer box after 1 µ of coarse-grained MD.

4. Summary

Ten spidroin models were achieved for the deliverable 2.5:

1. Spidroin 1 Atomistic monomeric model.
2. Spidroin 2 Atomistic monomeric model.
3. Spidroin 3 Atomistic monomeric model.
4. Spidroin 1 Atomistic tetrameric model.
5. Spidroin 2 Atomistic tetrameric model.
6. Spidroin 3 Atomistic tetrameric model.
7. Spidroin 1 Coarse-Grained monomeric model.
8. Spidroin 2 Coarse-Grained monomeric model.
9. Spidroin 3 Coarse-Grained monomeric model.
10. Spidroin 1 Coarse-Grained multimeric model.

References

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